

Ideal Gas Entropy as a Quasi-Deterministic Result of Removal of Time?

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In a previous note, we argued that an ideal gas consists of energy which does not depend on volume. In other words, there are N particles in a box and one may add energy in a Newtonian manner directly to these particles or in a second Newtonian deterministic manner through changing the volume and acting against pressure. This leads to two terms linked with energy: $dE = d B(T,V) - P dV$ ((1)). In a previous note, we found an expression for d (energy to particles) by assuming the existence of the ideal gas law $PV = nRT$. Here, we assume that one does not know this law. Here $B(T,V)$ is unknown.

In this note, we try to find out how ideal gas entropy arises. We argue that it seems to arise through the removal of time (i.e. measuring time for each particle in $x(t)$ in Newtonian mechanics which gives rise to $p(e_i)$). This automatically leads to a probabilistic scenario, but the question is: What probability is used? In (1), we showed that by considering a simple deterministic scenario of two constant velocity particles in two one dimensional boxes L and $2L$, a given x in L maps to various times. These times, however, map to two different points in $2L$ and so there is twice the uncertainty in $2L$ as in L . (We then generalized this to show that one has a uniform distribution). A uniform distribution is one in which the maximum amount of information is removed. We suggest that if this idea holds for volume, then it should also hold for $p(e_i)$. To find $p(e_i)$, one may then use $p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_3)p(e_4)$ and $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$. This leads to $p(e_i) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T)$. This result may be experimentally verified through pressure measurements.

Thus, we argue that removal of deterministic t (i.e. time measurements) of single particles leads to a deterministic type of probability, i.e. one with minimal information. Given that ((1)) implies that a particle is in equilibrium for tiny changes, this deterministic rule for probability (minimal information) must be imposed on V and T . As a second feature, one knows that if no energy is given directly to the single particles, then Newtonian mechanics suggests: $dE = -PdV$. This means that $d B(T,V)$ must be a function of T and V such that $dS=0$ in this case. In other words this function mimics both dE and $P dV$, i.e. carries physical information. For $V=\text{constant}$, $dE = d B(T,V_0)$. It has already been argued that $-T \ln(p(e_i)) + \ln(C(T))T = e_i$ information, so $\ln(V)$ should yield V information and fix the form of P (i.e. the ideal gas law) i.e P proportional to $1/V$.

Overall, we argue that ideal gas entropy emerges as a deterministic constraint (minimum information) on probabilities for e_i and V which arises when one removes a deterministic measurement, namely one on t . In other words, we argue that even though probabilities are used, there is a strong connection to deterministic Newtonian mechanics, especially since we show in (1) that $2V$ represents double the uncertainty as V through time removal of deterministic motion and not through stating that $2V$ has twice as many states (an statistical argument which is equivalent).

The Form of Entropy

If one has a box of volume V with N particles with kinetic energy, then the energy is:

$E =$ Sum over kinetic energy of single particles ((2))

One may change E in a Newtonian manner by making the volume smaller (hence imparting energy to the single particles or some of them) or adding energy directly to the single particles without changing V . Thus, it is not good enough to write:

$$dE = -PdV \text{ ((3a))}, \text{ but one needs: } dE = -PdV + d B(T,V) \text{ ((3b))}$$

If V is constant, then $dE = d B(T, V_0)$. On the other hand, T and V may change such that $d B(T,V)=0$ and then: $dE = -PdV$, the Newtonian result.

The question is then: What is $B(T,V)$? In a previous note we argued one may find this result by using the ideal gas law:

$$PV=nRT \text{ ((4))}$$

One also needs the result: $E = b T$, where b is a constant. One thing that does emerge from ((3b)) is that $d B(T,V)$ mimics information about both E and P . In this note, however, we wish to examine what $B(T,V)$ has to do with probability.

Removal of Time

A gas of N particles has some energy E . Why does one need to think in terms of probabilities in the first place? Newtonian mechanics states that one may follow particles along their trajectories, i.e. $x(t)$. The problem is that even in Newtonian mechanics, there is probability present in an elastic collision, because any collision which conserves momentum and energy is allowed. If one is only interested in E , then one does not need to know $p(e_i)$, but for pressure, one does, and pressure may be measured. At this point, there is no removal of time or any notion of maximization of number of states (as performed in a maximization of entropy subject to constraints problem).

Even if one acknowledges that there is probability in the outcomes of collisions, a particle may still be followed in time. Removing time, however, leads to the notion of $p(e_i)$ which describes the amount of time a single particle spends with energy e_i . It is assumed that all particles are the same. In other words, one no longer needs to follow the particle in time and may calculate pressure:

$$P = \frac{1}{3} \frac{1}{V} \int d^3p d^3v p v p(e_i) \text{ ((5))}$$

The problem is that one does not know $p(e_i)$.

We argue then that this begs the question: What is the effect of removing time from a deterministic problem because that is what is done to obtain the notion of $p(e_i)$?

In (1), we showed that one may consider two particles starting at $x=0, t=0$ with the same v in two one-dimensional containers of sizes L and $2L$. This is a deterministic Newtonian mechanics problem. We showed that if one removes time information (measurements), then picking an x

leads to a corresponding set of possible times which map to two different x points in $2L$. For $3L$, they map to 3 etc. Thus, removing time in a deterministic problem means that there is twice as much probability linked with $2L$ as with L . This is a key result, because it means that one cannot employ any probability distribution for position. In fact, the probability distribution which is linked with $2L$ having twice the uncertainty as L is:

A uniform distribution ((6))

A uniform distribution, however, is one with the least information. We have already argued that $B(T,V)$ must mimic the information of P and E . In the case of E , there should be a probability $p(e_i)$, but we argue that because of the removal of time result for L , one should also have minimal information. This means that for an elastic collision:

$$E_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((7a)) \quad \text{and} \quad p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_3)p(e_4) \quad \text{unnormalized} \quad ((7b))$$

This leads to: $p(e_i) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T)$ ((8))

In this case, one sees that $\ln(p(e_i))$ returns information about e_i and hence E and so one would expect that $\ln(1/V)$ should return information about P . In other words, this approach yields the ideal gas law.

As a result, the function $dB(T,V)$ which is $T dS(T,V)$ in ideal gas thermodynamics, is a function which contains probabilities which are governed according to a deterministic rule (minimal information) which follows from removing the measurement of time in a deterministic Newtonian problem. Thus, even though one moves from time measurements to probabilities $p(e_i)$ and $p_1(V)$, one does not have any $p(e_i)$ or $p(V)$. The results follow from the effects of removal of time from a deterministic analysis of two particles moving at constant v in two boxes, one of size L and the other of size $2L$.

From this, one may obtain the Sackur-Tetrode equation for entropy or $PV=nRT$. The $1/V$ is expected because of $d \ln(V) = dV/V$.

Conclusion

The key feature we wish to analyse in this note is the notion of why an entropy term should appear in the first place in an ideal gas and what its relation is to probability. It is usually taken as a fundamental result, that one should have minimal information in an ideal gas problem and entropy is considered as: $\ln\{ N! / \text{Product over } i n(e_i)! \}$. Stirling's approximation is then used and entropy is maximized according to a constraint: $E = \text{Sum over } i e_i p(e_i)$. $1/V$ represents the minimal knowledge of position. This seems reasonable if one has no information to suggest a bias, but does not really follow from deterministic Newtonian mechanics. Here we wish to introduce an approach that does follow from Newtonian mechanics. We suggest that this is one which creates $p(e_i)$ with time information/measurement removed. One may then see directly the effects of this. One sees the emergence of $p(e_i)$, but also of $p_1(V) = b1/V$ directly from removing time from a Newtonian problem ((1)). Thus, minimization of information is a direct consequence of removing time from a Newtonian problem and not simply a reasonable assumption. It leads to

$P_1(V) = 1/V$ and $p(e_i) = C(T)\exp(-e_i/T)$. In such a case, the entropy function imposes this constraint, mimicking both the information of E and P in the first law of thermodynamics.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Volume Information Entropy and Classical Mechanics (preprint, zenodo, 2025)